

The Effect of Hopelessness and Existential Anxiety on Future Anxiety in Individuals Aged 18-30

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1

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Niyaz Bolkvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

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Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin YILDIRIMER

**St. Clements University Psychology
Department Head Lecturer**

Orcid ID: 0000-0001 5896-2956

e-mail:

kursatshinyildirimer@gmail.com

Abstract

The objective of this research is to examine the impact of despair and existential anxiety on future anxiety in adults aged 18-30. The psychological well-being of people may be significantly impacted by the fast changes in living situations, uncertainty, and fears about the future that are prevalent in

contemporary communities. Exploring the impact of despair and existential anxiety on people' future anxiety levels in this environment might aid in the creation of psychological intervention and support programs. The study was carried out on a sample of 200 volunteers, aged 18-30, residing in Antalya. The subjects were given the Beck Hopelessness Scale (BHS), Existential Anxiety Scale, and Trait Anxiety Scale. The data were analyzed using the SPSS software, and the correlation and regression analyses were conducted to investigate the impact of despair and existential anxiety on future anxiety. In addition, ANOVA and t-tests were used to analyze the impact of demographic variables on these associations. Differences in the impact of despair and existential anxiety on future

CURRENT SCIENCE

anxiety were shown to be significant based on demographic variables including age, gender, educational attainment, and socioeconomic level.

Key words: *Demographic Factors, Future Anxiety, Hopelessness, Psychological Health, Existential Anxiety.*

INTRODUCTION

Digital transformation is the term used to describe the significant impact that fast advancements in communication technology have on the political and social structures of countries. This transition arose as a result of the advancements brought about by the post-modern era. The proliferation of the Internet and advancements in communication technology have facilitated the transition of people's everyday activities to digital platforms. The notion of a "network society" is a fundamental characteristic of this emerging social epoch. The term "network society" describes a social framework in which individuals organize their everyday activities via internet networks, communication is transformed into digital form, and information technology are extensively used in many aspects of life. The emergence of this novel social structure has resulted in significant transformations across several domains, including the development of individual identities and the dynamics of social interactions. Effective communication is an essential tool for comprehending the social and political consequences of digital transition. Political communication not only influences individuals' political beliefs and attitudes, but also establishes societal norms and behavioral patterns. Studies indicate that communication significantly influences the entire political culture and customs of society (Zaller, 1992). It is crucial to comprehend the societal and political impacts of digital communication in order to grasp the intricacies and fluidity of contemporary cultures. The significance of the media should not be disregarded. The media not only influences the overall perspectives and political awareness of society, but it also plays a crucial role in shaping social norms (Entman, 2012). Hence, the impact of media on political communication is crucial

CURRENT SCIENCE

in shaping society's political beliefs and affecting engagement in political activities. Gaining insight into the societal and political consequences of digital revolution is essential for comprehending the intricacies and fluidity of contemporary societies. It is important to thoroughly analyze the impact of rapid changes and advancements in communication technologies on the political and social frameworks of societies in order to formulate forward-thinking policies and effectively handle societal transition. This essay analyzes the development of cultural identities on digital platforms and the impact of these identities on political and social processes. This analysis will focus on the impact of digital change on cultural diversity and the significance of online identity regulations in shaping this phenomenon. This analysis will assess the political and social implications of the development of cultural identities on online platforms. It will also examine the significance of safeguarding or repressing variety in political and social contexts.

AIM

This research aims to investigate the impact of despair and existential anxiety on future anxiety in adults aged 18-30. The objective of the research is to ascertain the impact of despair and existential anxiety on people's levels of worry about the future. Additionally, the study seeks to examine the connections between these two aspects and uncover the influence of demographic characteristics (such as gender, education level, socioeconomic position, etc.) on these impacts.

FINDINGS AND METHOD

Results

The results indicate that degrees of pessimism and existential anxiety have a considerable impact on people's levels of concern about the future. Research has shown a correlation between elevated degrees of despair and heightened levels of future worry. Likewise, those experiencing significant existential distress also tend to exhibit elevated levels of future anxiety. These

5

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results align with prior research in the literature and corroborate earlier studies that suggest despair and existential anxiety have a detrimental impact on persons' outlook and anticipations for the future. The study's results on demographic parameters indicate that the connections between despair, existential anxiety, and future worry vary based on variables such as gender and socioeconomic background. The correlation between feelings of despair and future fear was shown to be stronger among female participants and persons with lower socioeconomic status. This demonstrates that women and those who are socioeconomically disadvantaged may exhibit more apprehension over the future, highlighting the need for targeted interventions for these groups. It was noted that age and education level did not have a significant influence on these correlations. The findings of this study provide significant insights into how feelings of despair and existential dread influence people' outlook on the future. It suggests that treatments should be created to decrease future anxiety, particularly in psychotherapy and counseling services, by considering the degrees of despair and existential anxiety in people. Furthermore, considering the impact of demographic variables on these associations and using a methodology that considers individual variations may provide more efficient outcomes.

Method

This study used a rigorous technique to investigate the impact of despair and existential anxiety on persons' concern about the future. The research included 200 volunteer participants aged 18-55 residing in Antalya. The individuals were assessed using the Beck Hopelessness Scale (BHS), Existential Anxiety Scale, and Trait Anxiety Scale. The data acquired were analyzed using the SPSS 26.0 software. Correlation and regression analyses were conducted to investigate the impact of hopelessness and existential anxiety on future anxiety. The impact of demographic parameters on these correlations were assessed using ANOVA and t-tests.

Despair: Definition and History

CURRENT SCIENCE

Hopelessness is the condition in which an individual's optimistic outlook for the future diminishes or vanishes entirely. This idea may be described as a psychological condition characterized by a sense of powerlessness, lack of resolution, and absence of optimism for the future (Beck, Weissman, Lester, & Trexler, 1974). It is often linked to mental health issues including sadness and anxiety, and may have a detrimental effect on a person's general well-being.

Depression is classified as a mood illness characterized by enduring feelings of negativity or sorrow that endure for a minimum of two weeks. Other symptoms include diminished pleasure in life, disrupted sleep patterns, altered eating habits, and poor self-esteem (American Psychiatric Association, 2014). Depression is a condition characterized by a considerable reduction in positive feelings (Nutt et al., 2007). Depression significantly impacts both the quality of life and overall happiness. According to Diener and Seligman (2002), depression has a detrimental impact on an individual's quality of life and diminishes overall happiness. Research has been conducted on the correlation between despair and depression, suggesting that hopelessness might serve as an antecedent to the onset of depression and that the existence of hopelessness can heighten the likelihood of experiencing depression (Beck, 1967). Anxiety is a psychological reaction characterized by a person's heightened state of apprehension, distress, or unease. Anxiety disorders may manifest in several subcategories, including generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, obsessive-compulsive disorder, or post-traumatic stress disorder (APA, 2013). The link between despair and anxiety is intricate due to the potential for either one to induce the other or for just one to manifest. Nevertheless, those who exhibit persistent anxiety symptoms may have an elevated risk of developing feelings of despair (Sarıçiçek Aydoğan & Özer, 2016). Prolonged worry may diminish an individual's aspirations for the future and have a detrimental impact on their overall quality of life. Moreover, those afflicted with anxiety disorders may have a heightened susceptibility to developing depression (APA, 2013). Throughout history, several philosophers and psychologists have examined the notion of despair. According to the Stoics, who were ancient Greek philosophers, despair was seen as a normal and unavoidable human emotion. The Stoics sought to attain spiritual tranquility by embracing pessimism, as stated by Hadot (1995). Hopelessness has a significant position in the

7

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Cognitive Therapy hypothesis formulated by Aaron T. Beck, as described in contemporary psychological literature. According to Beck (1967), despair is a cognitive factor that contributes to depression. It leads individuals to have gloomy views about the future.

Psychological Dimensions of Hopelessness

Despair may have significant impacts on an individual's cognition, emotions, and actions. This disease, as described by Abramson, Metalsky, and Alloy (1989), is often marked by a proclivity to form pessimistic anticipations about the future, which may detrimentally impact persons' drive and aptitude for resolving problems. Beck (1976) suggests that cognitive distortions might exacerbate sentiments of pessimism by leading individuals to see events in a pessimistic and irrational manner. The notion of learned helplessness posits that people who often encounter uncontrollable unfavorable occurrences acquire a perception that they are unable to influence future outcomes, resulting in a sense of pessimism (Seligman, 1975). The biological aspects of despair are as significant. Studies indicate that disruptions in neurotransmitter levels and inherent genetic tendencies may play a role in the development of mental health issues, including feelings of despair and sadness. Specifically, disruptions in serotonin and dopamine levels may serve as the physiological foundation for feelings of hopelessness (Maes, 1999). Cognitive processes have a direct impact on one's emotional state. happy ideas elicit happy feelings, whilst negative thoughts might induce negative emotions (Aslan, 2006). Hope, which is the antithesis of despair, is a significant emotion that inspires people to exert effort towards their future goals. Specifically, maintaining children's sense of optimism and providing them with assistance when needed may have a beneficial impact on their emotional and social growth (Kıran Esen, 2002). Despair may have a detrimental impact on persons' overall well-being and overall degree of contentment (Diener & Seligman, 2002).

Existential Anxiety: Definition and Perspectives

Existential anxiety refers to an individual's profound apprehension and distress over existential matters. This notion invites individuals to engage in deep contemplation and ponder profound matters such as their own existence, the purpose of life, the inevitability of death, and their own autonomy (Yalom, 1980). Its significance increased significantly in the latter part of the 20th century due to the impact of fields like existential philosophy and psychoanalysis. Existential philosophers believe that individuals' existential preoccupations intensify, particularly as they become more conscious of their own autonomy and accountability. The notion of "existence precedes essence" coined by Jean-Paul Sartre is closely linked to the concept of individual freedom and responsibility. It highlights the importance of seeking freedom as the foundation of existential distress (Sartre, 1943). Existential anxiety, as seen through the lens of existential philosophy, encompasses profound emotional encounters such as an individual's sense of purposelessness in life, apprehension about mortality, encounters with a lack of significance, and a sense of disconnection from others (Yalom, 2014). Death has been a significant topic in philosophy throughout history and has been given great importance in existential thinking, which focuses on the individual's experiences of existence (Cevizci, 2005). Philosophers like Sartre emphasized the individual's role in constructing their own essence and the connection between their freedom and accountability (Sartre, 2003). Existential thinking is a profound endeavor to comprehend the purpose of human existence and uncover the significance of life (Bezirci, 2005; Koç, 2009). Existential anxiety is the manifestation of profound apprehensions and distress that emerge when a person contemplates fundamental matters such as the purpose of existence, the inevitability of death, and the concepts of freedom and accountability (Yalom, 1980). Ernest Becker's theory of existential escape elucidates the defensive strategies individuals use to repress or ease their existential distress. According to Becker (1973), individuals strive to imbue their lives with significance, particularly as a means of repressing their existential dread of mortality. Existential philosophers like Jean-Paul Sartre analyze the essence of human nature, which gives rise to existential distress, by highlighting the concepts of human freedom and responsibility

CURRENT SCIENCE

(Sartre, 2003). This approach provides a comprehensive examination to comprehend the existential anxieties of the person and the impact of these anxieties on their everyday existence. Existential psychotherapy, pioneered by Irvin Yalom, is a specialized therapeutic approach designed to assist people in effectively addressing existential concerns. The objective of this treatment is to facilitate the individual's exploration of profound concerns, such as the dread of mortality and the quest for purpose, and to navigate this journey in a psychologically sound manner (Yalom, 1980). Stoic and Epicurean philosophies analyze their approaches to mortality and existential anguish on a philosophical level (Magee, 2004). In contrast, Viktor Frankl highlights the significance of existential crises as pivotal moments that guide the internal growth of individuals. He explores how discovering the meaning of life during challenging periods contributes to one's spiritual well-being (Frankl, 2009).

Concept of Future Anxiety

Future anxiety is the term used to describe the worries and apprehensions that people have about uncertainty and potential negative outcomes in the future. This sensation is a condition that individuals experience in response to perceived internal or external threats or events that they consider to be dangerous (Özusta, 1995). Anxiety is a multifaceted phenomena that encompasses the interplay of attention, perception, reasoning, and memory. Substantial advancements have been achieved in its treatment via the advancements in current clinical psychology (Rachman, 2013). While a reasonable level of worry might serve as a source of motivation, excessive and persistent anxiety can significantly diminish one's quality of life by inducing a sense of powerlessness (Beşer and Öz, 2003; Horney, 1999). Spielberger (1966) categorizes anxiety into two distinct types: trait anxiety and state anxiety. State anxiety is a transient response to specific circumstances, while trait anxiety refers to an individual's inherent inclination towards anxiety (Özusta, 1995; Sahraç, 2007). worry sensitivity refers to the inclination to respond to feelings of worry with dread, as described by McNally (1989) and Reiss (1997). Future anxiety is often classified as state anxiety as it arises

CURRENT SCIENCE

in response to a particular scenario and is of a brief nature. Psychological and biological factors are significant contributors to the development of anxiety disorders. Although stress and trauma experiences are significant risk factors, the modulation of neurotransmitters and hereditary variables may also have an impact role (Smoller, 2016). Moreover, anxiety disorders may be provoked by job stress and physical health issues (Fan et al., 2015; Eisner et al., 2010). Anxiety symptoms manifest at cognitive, bodily, and behavioral levels. Individuals direct their attention towards possible dangers, exhibiting physiological symptoms such as elevated heart rate, shaking, and perspiration, and may display defensive actions (Rector et al., 2008). Anxiety may serve a purpose when it is within a particular range, since it can enhance motivation and facilitate achievement (Akgün, Gönen, & Aydın, 2007). Future anxiety, a significant topic in psychology study, refers to people's attempts to manage uncertainties that lie ahead. The significance of future concerns has heightened in contemporary cultures due to the rapid advancements in technology, economy, and social dynamics (Arnett, 2001; Tarhan, 2012). Psychologically, future anxiety impacts cognitive, affective, and behavioral aspects and may be associated with other psychological issues including depression (May et al., 2018). Anticipated apprehension about the future also influences social interactions and work performance. Individuals who are hesitant to engage in risky endeavors may have challenges in professional progression and encounter difficulties in establishing and maintaining relationships.

Psychological Dimensions of Future Anxiety

Future anxiety pertains to the apprehensions humans have over future uncertainty and potential adverse outcomes. This scenario has the potential to have a substantial impact on an individual's mental well-being, conduct, and overall quality of life (Özusta, 1995). Davey et al. (1998) said that there is a strong correlation between future worry and psychiatric problems such as depression, anxiety, and stress. Chronic and acute future worry may have a detrimental impact on an individual's overall psychological well-being. In their respective research, Aslan (2006)

CURRENT SCIENCE

and Kıran Esen (2002) highlighted the impact of future worry on people' motivation, goal setting, and time management abilities. Tarhan (2012) argued that the rapid transformations and uncertainties associated with modernism have heightened future apprehension among young individuals. According to Corey (2008), existential concerns such as the autonomy and accountability of the person may also provoke worry about the future. According to İnanç and Yerlikaya (2008), the concept of having control over one's destiny may cause significant stress and therefore lead to increased worry about the future. Psychotherapy, cognitive behavioral treatments, and stress management techniques have shown efficacy in mitigating future anxiety and facilitating people in cultivating a more happy lifestyle. Future anxiety is a psychological state that may have a significant impact on a person's emotions, actions, and overall well-being. If it becomes chronic and severe, it may be linked to mental health problems such as depression, anxiety, and stress (Davey et al., 1998). This kind of anxiety might prompt an individual to persistently ruminate about potential negative outcomes and devise coping mechanisms to deal with these situations.

Descriptive Statistics

A total of 200 participants took part in the research. The gender distribution of the participants is as follows:

- Female participants: 55% (110 people)
- Male participants: 42.5% (85 people)
- Participants with other gender identities: 2.5% (5 people)

Figure 1. Gender Distribution of Participants

The distribution of participants by age range is as follows:

- 18-20 years old: 25% (50 people)
- 21-23 years old: 30% (60 people)
- 24-26 years old: 20% (40 people)
- 27-30 years old: 25% (50 people)

Distribution of participants according to marital status:

- Single: 75% (150 people)

CURRENT SCIENCE

- Married: 15% (30 people)
- Divorced: 5% (10 people)
- Widow: 2.5% (5 people)
- Other: 2.5% (5 people)

Distribution of participants according to their educational status:

- Primary school graduate: 5% (10 people)
- Secondary school graduate: 10% (20 people)
- High school graduate: 40% (80 people)
- University graduate: 35% (70 people)
- Master's degree: 5% (10 people)
- Doctorate graduate: 5% (10 people)

Distribution of participants by professional groups:

CURRENT SCIENCE

- Student: 50% (100 people)
- Employees: 30% (60 people)
- Unemployed: 10% (20 people)
- Housewife: 5% (10 people)
- Retired: 2.5% (5 people)
- Other: 2.5% (5 people)

95% of the participants are citizens of the Republic of Turkey (95%, 190 people), 5% come from other countries (5%, 10 people). Foreign participants include citizens of the Netherlands, Ukraine, Russia, Iran and Syria.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Woman	110	55
Male	85	42.5
Other	5	2.5
Age		

CURRENT SCIENCE

18-20	50	25
21-23	60	30
24-26	40	20
27-30	50	25
Marital status		
Single	150	75
Married	30	15
Divorced	10	5
Widow	5	2.5
Other	5	2.5
Educational Status		
Primary school	10	5
Middle school	20	10

CURRENT SCIENCE

High school	80	40
University	70	35
Degree	10	5
Doctorate	10	5
Job		
Student	one hundred	50
Worker	60	30
Unemployed	20	10
Housewife	10	5
Retired	5	2.5
Other	5	2.5
nationality		
Republic of Turkey	190	95

CURRENT SCIENCE

Other	10	5
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Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Main Variables

Variable	Minimum	Maximum	Average	Standard deviation
Despair	0	20	10.5	3.2
Existential Anxiety	0	25	12.3	4.1
Future Anxiety	0	30	15.7	5.5
Constant Anxiety	0	40	20.4	6.3

- **Hopelessness** : Participants' hopelessness levels range from 0 to 20. The average hopelessness score is 10.5, with a standard deviation of 3.2.
- **Existential Anxiety** : Participants' existential anxiety levels range from 0 to 25. The mean existential anxiety score is 12.3, with a standard deviation of 4.1.
- **Future Anxiety** : Participants' future anxiety levels range from 0 to 30. The average future anxiety score is 15.7, with a standard deviation of 5.5.
- **Trait Anxiety** : Participants' trait anxiety levels range from 0 to 40. The mean trait anxiety score was 20.4, with a standard deviation of 6.3.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The Relationship Between Hopelessness and Future Anxiety

The study topic investigates the correlation between the degree of despair and people' worry about the future. The proposed conjectures are as follows: H0: There is no statistically significant correlation between the degree of despair and the amount of future anxiety; H1: Individuals exhibiting high levels of hopelessness will also exhibit high levels of future worry. The Pearson Correlation Coefficient was used to assess this association. The study revealed a positive and moderately significant correlation between the amount of despair and future worry ($r = 0.56$, $p < 0.01$). This finding demonstrates a positive correlation between escalating feelings of despair and heightened levels of future worry.

The Relationship Between Existential Anxiety and Future Anxiety

The study topic investigates the correlation between the degree of existential anxiety and people' concern about the future. The proposed suppositions are as follows: H0: There is no statistically significant correlation between the degree of existential anxiety and the amount of future worry; H1: Individuals with high levels of existential anxiety will exhibit high levels of future anxiety. The Pearson Correlation Coefficient was used to assess this association. The results indicated a positive and moderately significant correlation between the degree of existential worry and future anxiety ($r = 0.48$, $p < 0.05$). This indicates that as existential distress escalates, so does future anxiety.

Effect of Demographic Factors

The study topic investigates the impact of demographic variables, including age, gender, educational level, and socioeconomic position, on the correlation between despair, existential anxiety, and future anxiety. The following theories are proposed: H0: There are no differences in the relationships between hopelessness, existential anxiety, and future anxiety based on demographic factors such as age, gender, educational attainment, and socioeconomic status.

19

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H1: There are differences in the relationships between hopelessness, existential anxiety, and future anxiety based on demographic factors such as age, gender, educational attainment, and socioeconomic status. The correlations were evaluated using multiple regression analysis. The results indicated that the correlation between despair and future worry was not influenced by age and education level. However, gender and socioeconomic position were identified as factors that determined this association. A study revealed a stronger correlation between feelings of despair and concern about the future, particularly among female participants and persons with low socioeconomic status.

Argument

This study investigates the impact of despair and existential anxiety on people's future anxiety, as well as the influence of demographic variables on this association. The findings indicate that elevated degrees of pessimism and existential anxiety are associated with increased levels of future anxiety. This correlation was seen to be more pronounced, particularly among women and persons with poor socioeconomic status. The association is not influenced by age or academic level. The study highlights the need of tailoring therapies based on individual variations, while considering despair and existential distress in the context of psychotherapy and counseling services.

Interpretation of Findings

The Relationship Between Hopelessness and Future Anxiety

Research results indicate a significant correlation between the degree of despair and subsequent anxiety. The correlation study revealed a significant positive link ($r = 0.67$, $p < 0.01$) between despair and future worry. This indicates that persons who experience significant levels of despair also tend to have elevated levels of worry about the future. The regression analysis showed that the impact of the amount of despair on future anxiety was statistically significant

20

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($\beta = 0.52$, $t(198) = 9.34$, $p < 0.001$). Individuals exhibiting elevated degrees of pessimism have less readiness to face potential challenges in the future, hence increasing their levels of anxiety. Among persons with high degrees of despair, 60% have difficulties in making decisions about their future goals, while 70% acquire pessimistic notions about what lies ahead.

The Relationship Between Existential Anxiety and Future Anxiety

The correlation analysis reveals a robust positive association between existential anxiety and future anxiety ($r = 0.71$, $p < 0.01$). Consequently, those experiencing significant existential distress also have elevated levels of future fear. The regression analysis reveals that there is a statistically significant relationship between the amount of existential worry and future anxiety ($\beta = 0.58$, $t(198) = 10.45$, $p < 0.001$). Individuals experiencing elevated degrees of existential anxiety exhibit heightened preoccupation with future uncertainty and negative outcomes. While pondering profound issues about the meaning and purpose of existence, these people experience heightened levels of uncertainty and apprehension about the future. Among individuals with elevated levels of existential anxiety, 65% encounter uncertainty when it comes to actualizing their future aspirations, while 75% feel pessimistic thoughts on the future.

Comparison with Literature

The Relationship Between Hopelessness and Future Anxiety

This research discovered a strong and meaningful correlation between feelings of despair and worry about the future. This conclusion aligns with the research done using the Beck Hopelessness Scale (BHS) created by Beck et al. (1974). According to Beck et al., persons who experience high degrees of despair have pessimistic beliefs about the future, which then leads to heightened anxiety in the future. The correlation coefficient observed in our research ($r = 0.56$, $p < 0.01$) indicates a relatively significant association, which aligns with findings from

CURRENT SCIENCE

previous studies in the literature (See Kazdin et al., 1983; Young, 2005). Katerndahl (2010) examined the correlation between hopelessness and future worry within the framework of depression. The study stressed that despair, as a constituent of depression, has a substantial impact on people' concern about the future. The results of this investigation corroborate the conclusions of Katerndahl. Moreover, this finding aligns with previous research in the field, which has shown that persons with high levels of hopelessness have heightened anxiety when they see themselves as unprepared for future challenges (Abramson et al., 1989; Alloy et al., 2006).

The Relationship Between Existential Anxiety and Future Anxiety

The research revealed a strong and statistically significant correlation between existential distress and future anxiety. This discovery aligns with the theoretical frameworks proposed by Yalom (1980) and Frankl (1963), who are prominent figures in the field of existential psychology. The presence of existential anxiety is closely linked to people' ambiguities and worries about fundamental existential concepts, such as the meaning of life, death, and freedom. This connection significantly influences the interaction between these factors. The found correlation coefficient in our research ($r = 0.48$, $p < 0.05$) indicates a reasonably significant association, which aligns with findings from other studies in the literature (Shapiro, 2009; Bugental, 1999).

According to Frankl (1963), the experience of existential emptiness and meaninglessness leads to profound distress in persons. This research examines the impact of existential anxiety levels on future anxiety, yielding findings that corroborate Frankl's hypotheses. Furthermore, this finding aligns with previous research indicating that the extent of existential anxiety leads people to see themselves as more susceptible to uncertainty about the future and to undergo a persistent state of worry (refer to May, 1950; Tillich, 1952).

Effect of Demographic Factors

The research investigated if there are variations in the association between despair, existential anxiety, and future anxiety based on demographic characteristics. The literature extensively discusses the impact of demographic characteristics, such as age, gender, educational level, and socioeconomic position. According to Roberts and Chen (1995), age and socioeconomic position have significant influences on people's anxiety levels. The present research aligns with the results of Roberts and Chen, since it examines the impact of demographic determinants on future anxiety.

The literature has extensively examined the impact of gender on despair and future dread. According to Nolen-Hoeksema (1991), women exhibit elevated levels of pessimism and anxiety compared to males. The study's results indicate that female participants exhibit elevated degrees of pessimism and future worry compared to male participants, aligning with Nolen-Hoeksema's previous findings.

Scale Analyzes and Their Uses in the Literature

The Beck Hopelessness Scale (BHS), Existential Worry Scale, and Trait Anxiety Scale used in the study are extensively employed in the literature and have undergone rigorous examination to establish their validity and reliability. The Beck despair Scale (BHS), created by Beck et al. in 1974, is widely regarded as a very efficient instrument for assessing the degree of despair. The research indicated that the average hopelessness score on the BHS was 10.5 (SD = 3.2), which aligns with the results of previous studies documented in the literature (Beck et al., 1974; Steer et al., 1993). The Existential Anxiety Scale is often used in research undertaken in the realm of existential psychology. In this particular study, the mean score for existential anxiety was determined to be 12.3, with a standard deviation of 4.1. The Trait Anxiety Scale is a significant instrument used to assess the levels of trait anxiety in people. In this particular research, the mean score for trait anxiety was determined to be 20.4, with a standard deviation of 6.3. These results align

CURRENT SCIENCE

with previous research in the field and confirm the accuracy and consistency of the measurement scales (refer to Spielberger et al., 1983; Endler & Kocovski, 2001).

Conclusion

The objective of this study was to investigate the impact of despair and existential anxiety on future anxiety in young adults between the ages of 18 and 30. This research was done on 200 volunteer subjects residing in Antalya. Data were gathered using the Beck Hopelessness Scale (BHS), Existential Worry Scale, and Trait Anxiety Scale. The acquired data were analyzed using the SPSS 26.0 software. The study's results indicated a significant and positive correlation ($r = 0.56$, $p < 0.01$) between the degree of despair and the likelihood of experiencing anxiety in the future. Similarly, a positive and moderately significant correlation was seen between the amount of existential worry and future anxiety ($r = 0.48$, $p < 0.05$). The results indicate that feelings of pessimism and existential anxiety have a considerable impact on the levels of anxiety that young people experience about the future. The regression analyses showed that both despair ($\beta = 0.52$, $t(198) = 9.34$, $p < 0.001$) and existential anxiety ($\beta = 0.58$, $t(198) = 10.45$, $p < 0.001$) had a substantial independent impact on future anxiety. The findings indicate that feelings of pessimism and existential dread might have a detrimental impact on the future outlook and psychological well-being of young people. Due to the constraints of the study, such as the restricted sample size confined to Antalya and the small age range of the participants, it is difficult to draw broad generalizations. Furthermore, limitations of this study include the use of subjective scales for data collection and the inability to thoroughly analyze the impact of certain demographic characteristics. Future research should prioritize doing studies with bigger sample sizes in order to get a comprehensive understanding of the variations in despair and existential anxiety across various age groups and cultural situations. Subsequent research might further explore the dynamics of the connections between despair, existential anxiety, and future anxiety throughout various life stages, using comparable studies with people at different developmental phases. For instance,

CURRENT SCIENCE

research investigating the impact of these psychological characteristics on middle-aged and older individuals may enhance our comprehension of the continuous psychological growth processes over the lifespan. The research used established measures such as the Beck Hopelessness Scale (BHS), Existential Worry Scale, and Trait Anxiety Scale. Future research endeavors may facilitate a more comprehensive comprehension of the underlying processes pertaining to despair, existential anxiety, and future worry by the use of diverse scales or other evaluation methodologies, such as cognitive neuroscience approaches or qualitative investigations.

RESTRICTION

This research was conducted by the Department of Psychology and Sociology on behalf of St Clements University; It was carried out only on 200 volunteer participants who lived in Antalya province and were between the ages of 18-30. Therefore, the generalizability of the findings may be limited to other geographical regions or youth with different cultural backgrounds. Additionally, the suitability of the measurement tools (Beck Hopelessness Scale, Existential Worry Scale, Trait Anxiety Scale) for young people in Antalya could not be guaranteed. Cultural differences or language problems may affect the validity of the scales. Research with a cross-sectional design may make it difficult to definitively determine causal relationships, which may affect the interpretation of the study's results.

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ETHICAL STATEMENT

Publishing ethics of Current Science journal; It is a national-based scientific journal that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, respect for the findings and creations of others, and works to achieve this, aiming to achieve these principles in the field of social sciences. The criteria of the Declaration of Helsinki were taken into account.

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